

2025 STOCK ASSESSMENT OF SPOTTED SEATROUT *CYNOSCION NEBULOSUS* IN ALABAMA

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Abbreviations

ADCNR	Alabama Department of Conservation and Natural Resources
ADSEFR	Alabama Deep Sea Fishing Rodeo
AIC	Akaike Information Criterion
AL	Alabama
ALSPT	Alabama stock of Spotted Seatrout
AMRD	Alabama Marine Resources Division
BSP	AMRD Biological Sampling Program
CAAL	Conditional age-at-length
CV	Coefficient of variation
F	Fishing mortality
GAM	Generalized Additive Model
GNS	AMRD Gill Net Survey
LWR	Length-weight relationship
M	Natural mortality
MASE	Mean absolute scaled error
MSL	Minimum size limit
MSY	Maximum sustainable yield
MRIP	Marine Recreational Information Program
NOAA Fisheries	National Marine Fisheries Service
RMSE	Root mean squared error
SS3	Stock Synthesis
SPR	Spawning potential ratio
SPT	Spotted Seatrout
VBGF	Von Bertalanffy Growth Function

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Alabama stock of Spotted Seatrout *Cynoscion nebulosus* (ALSPT) was assessed using a statistical catch-at-age modeling framework (Stock Synthesis 3) for the period 1950-2023. The previous assessment suggested that the ALSPT resource was overfished and experiencing overfishing during the terminal year (2016). The current assessment input data included updated life history information, commercial and recreational landings, recreational dead discards, a fishery-independent relative abundance index, and length and conditional age-at-length compositions from fishery-dependent and fishery-independent sources. The assessment indicates that the ALSPT resource was severely depleted in the early 2000s due to high levels of harvest and poor recruitment. This period was followed by increased recruitment, improving stock condition while continuing to support high levels of harvest. In the late 2010s, stock condition was reducing, leading to a management intervention in 2019, which greatly reduced harvest and fishing mortality rates for the remainder of the time series. The assessment strongly suggests that the ALSPT resource is in the best condition it has been in decades, and that the most recent management intervention was a successful one.

NOTABLE CHANGES TO PREVIOUS ASSESSMENT

- Updated life history parameters, including growth, length-weight relationship, and natural mortality
- Parameterization of natural mortality informed using multiple longevity-based estimators
- Internal estimation of growth parameters (e.g., asymptotic length)
- Age treatment was updated to conditional age-at-length
- Relative abundance index standardization performed using a generalized additive model framework
- Biological composition data weighting using the Francis method
- Robust model diagnostics were conducted, including jitter analysis, likelihood profiles, runs tests, joint residual plots, hindcast cross-validation, and retrospectives
- Sensitivity runs to evaluate modelling assumptions

INTRODUCTION

RELEVANCE

Spotted Seatrout *Cynoscion nebulosus* (SPT) are an inshore species distributed across the U.S. South Atlantic and Gulf of Mexico coasts. They support valuable inshore fisheries for their aggressive angling behavior and great table fare. SPT used to heavily support commercial fisheries in the 1900s; however, this has changed as states have limited harvest to the recreational sector in recent decades. In Alabama (AL), SPT (ALSPT) is among the most targeted inshore species by recreational anglers. In 2024, there were >400 thousand recreational fishing trips in which ALSPT was the primary or secondary target species in AL (NOAA Fisheries 2024).

MANAGEMENT HISTORY

Commercial harvest of ALSPT can be traced back to the early 1900s but ceased in 1985 when the species was designated game fish status, allowing harvest exclusively to the recreational sector (Bohaboy et al. 2018; ADCNR 2019a). Regulation for the ALSPT recreational sector began in 1978, with a minimum size limit (MSL) of 12" (30.5 cm) total length (TL) and a daily bag limit of 50 fish per person (Bohaboy et al. 2018). These harvest restrictions were subsequently increased several times, and by 1986, the MSL was increased to 14" (35.6 cm) TL, and the bag limit was reduced to 10 fish per person (Bohaboy et al. 2018). This regulation included an undersized allowance, which was removed in 2000 (Bohaboy et al. 2018). Following an assessment indicating that ALSPT was overfished and experiencing overfishing (Bohaboy et al. 2018), the recreational regulations were modified in 2019 from a MSL into a slot limit to allow the harvest of 6 fish in the 15-22" (38.1-55.9 cm) TL range with one of those allowed to be overslot (ADCNR 2019b, 2022). A summarized version of the management history is presented in Table 1.

DATA SOURCES

LIFE HISTORY

AGE AND GROWTH

The age and growth of ALSPT were updated using two sources: 1) the fishery-dependent Alabama Marine Resources Division (AMRD) Biological Sampling Program (BSP) and the fishery-independent AMRD Gill Net Survey (GNS; see [Relative Abundance Index section for more details on this survey](#)). Both collect a suite of biological information (e.g., sex, lengths, weights, and ages). Collected ALSPT sagittal otoliths from both surveys were processed and aged by AMRD personnel, and annuli counts were provided for this assessment. Given that the BSP samples received two independent age estimations, only samples with agreement between reads were used (127 samples out of 2268 were removed). Samples used to model age and growth were collected during 2002-2023 for BSP and during 2000-2023 for GNS. It was evident that catches were female-skewed ~2:1 (Table 2, further discussed in [Discussion and Research Recommendations](#)).

Before developing growth models, fractional ages were obtained using the catch date and assuming a mean birth date of July 1st. Sexual dimorphism in SPT is strongly documented (Blanchet et al. 2001; Carroll and Lowerre-Barbieri 2019). Therefore, sex-specific growth models were developed. Analyses were conducted in R using the “Estimate_Growth()” function from the “AquaticLifeHistory” package (<https://jonathansmart.github.io/AquaticLifeHistory/>). This approach provided parameters for multiple models (e.g., von Bertalanffy [VBGF], Logistic, and Gompertz), comparison between models (via Akaike Information Criterion [AIC]), and associated bootstrapped (n=1000) confidence intervals. The VBGF was used in the stock assessment given its common application for fish and availability in the modelling framework, but the Logistic model was statistically the best fit for females (corrected AIC >40 units higher for VBGF, Figure 1).

LENGTH-WEIGHT RELATIONSHIP

The sex-specific length-weight relationship (LWR) was updated using three data sources: 1) BSP, 2) GNS, and 3) the Alabama Deep Sea Fishing Rodeo (ADSFR). The ADSFR data consisted of fishery-dependent samples collected during the annual tournament and recorded information on sex, length, and weight. Samples used to model the LWRs were collected during 2006-2023 for BSP, 2000-2024 for GNS, and 2011-2024 for ADSFR.

Sex-specific LWRs were developed using the log-transformed linear model approach. Total lengths (cm) and whole weight (kg) were natural-log transformed, then a linear

Recreational discards were obtained the same way as the recreational catch, but the query parameter “type of catch” was changed to “Released alive (Type B2)”. This method provided the annual number of fish released alive. These were used to calculate dead discards using a 10% discard mortality rate, then converted from numbers of fish to biomass using an average weight of 2kg (see [Sensitivity Runs](#) for alternative approach tested). Finally, these were added to the yearly recreational catch before being added to the assessment.

BIOLOGICAL COMPOSITIONS

LENGTH COMPOSITIONS

Recreational length compositions were obtained from the NOAA Fisheries MRIP web portal (<https://www.fisheries.noaa.gov/data-tools/recreational-fisheries-statistics-queries>). The “Length Frequencies” option under “Catch Data” was queried using the information in Table 6.

Fishery-independent length compositions from the GNS were used. These were filtered similar to the GNS index standardization protocol (see [Relative Abundance Index](#)). The GNS length composition samples were collected during 2000-2023.

CONDITIONAL AGE-AT-LENGTH COMPOSITIONS

Conditional age-at-length (CAAL) data came from two sources: 1) BSP and 2) GNS. This approach provided variability in ALSPT length-at-age and is required for attempting to estimate growth parameters within the assessment (Lee et al. 2019, 2024). The conditional age-at-length data were collected during 2002-2023 for BSP and 2000-2023 for GNS.

RELATIVE ABUNDANCE INDEX

ALABAMA MARINE RESOURCES DIVISION GILL NET SURVEY

The GNS was used to develop a fishery-independent relative abundance index for age-1+ ALSPT. The GNS is one of the primary surveys used to monitor recreationally and commercially important fishes in coastal AL. Catch and biological composition data from GNS are essential for monitoring trends and conducting assessments like the one presented here.

The GNS uses a stratified random sampling approach stratified by area (upper Mobile Bay, lower Mobile Bay, Mississippi Sound, and Perdido Bay) and net type (small or large mesh). The small mesh gill net is composed of five panels (150ft each) of graduated mesh sizes (750ft total), with mesh sizes ranging from 2" to 4" in ½" increments. The large mesh gill net is composed of four panels (150ft each) of graduated mesh sizes (600ft

total), with mesh sizes ranging from 4.5" to 6" in ½" increments. Small mesh and large mesh gill nets are set perpendicular and parallel to the shoreline, respectively. The orientation of the net set can be modified when necessary (e.g., rapid depth change). Both nets are soaked ideally for at least ~1hr unless conditions deem otherwise.

Stations are randomly selected within each sampling area each month. At each station, fish are identified and enumerated. The first 10 individuals of target species are sampled for sex, weight, length, and age (using sagittal otolith sections). Environmental and water quality data collected *in situ* include date, time, location, soak time, temperature, salinity, dissolved oxygen, depth, net set orientation, and sampling area. For the purposes of this assessment, only the small mesh gill net catches were used to create a relative abundance index. The large mesh gill net was omitted as this gear rarely captured ALSPT and is intended for capturing flounder (*Paralichthys spp.*). Stations from Perdido Bay were excluded due to smaller sample sizes (Figure 4).

Generalized additive models were used to generate a standardized relative abundance index using the "gam()" function from the "mgcv" package (<https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/mgcv/mgcv.pdf>). Candidate covariates included year as a factor variable, and depth, temperature, dissolved oxygen, and salinity as numerical variables with smoothers (cubic splines). Collinearity between the numerical variables was assessed by calculating Spearman coefficients using the "cor()" function in R. All coefficients were well below 0.3 (and -0.3) except for temperature and dissolved oxygen which displayed moderate strength (-0.6) as expected. All GAMs were fit using Restricted Maximum Likelihood.

Error distributions explored included Gaussian, Tweedie, Poisson, negative binomial with no transformation, log transformation, and 4th root transformation of the response variable (ALSPT catch). While single and delta (modelling presence and abundance separately) approaches were investigated, a single-model approach with a negative binomial error type and 4th root transformation was selected after evaluating quantile-quantile plots of the full models across error and transformation types. Then, the final model selection was conducted using an all-subsets approach. This was done using the "dredge()" function from the "MuMIn" package (<https://cloud.r-project.org/web/packages/MuMIn/MuMIn.pdf>). This approach generates all possible combinations from the full model and allows the user to specify specific covariates to retain (the year covariate was retained). Additionally, this process provides a list of all possible model combinations ranked by AIC and deviance explained. The final model retained the year, temperature, and salinity covariates. Pairwise concurvity was evaluated using the "concurvity()" function from the "gratia" package (<https://gavinsimpson.github.io/gratia/index.html>) and no strong concurvity was observed (<0.2).

A bootstrapping approach was used to estimate year effects on ALSPT catch by resampling 10,000 predictions at mean values of the retained covariates (temperature and salinity). The point estimates were used to determine yearly 95% confidence intervals, standard deviation, and coefficient of variation ([CV] indicates precision of estimates and is a necessary assessment input). Finally, the response was back-transformed to be used in the assessment (Figure 5).

STOCK ASSESSMENT MODEL CONFIGURATION AND METHODS

MODEL CONFIGURATION

MODEL CONFIGURATION

A statistical catch-at-age model was conducted using Stock Synthesis ([SS3], v 3.30.22.beta) (Methot and Wetzel 2013). The SS3 framework is among the most widely used and flexible approaches for assessing fishery species and providing management advice. The modeling approach consisted of three linked modules: 1) a population dynamics module, 2) an observation module, and 3) a likelihood function that integrates different data components' fits into an overall likelihood objective function. The framework provides estimates of key quantities, such as recruitment, abundance, spawning stock biomass, and exploitation rates. Modeling was conducted using the Stock Assessment Continuum Tool (<https://github.com/shcaba/SS-DL-tool>), which is a web application front end that builds SS3 files and runs those models, and provides diagnostics and model outputs.

INITIAL CONDITIONS

The ALSPT assessment begins in 1950 with the terminal year of 2023 and assumes that the stock is in virgin condition during the initial year.

TEMPORAL AND SPATIAL STRUCTURE

The ALSPT population was modeled from age-0 to age-9+, with the last bin representing a plus group. There was no seasonal component since removals and data collection occur throughout the year. The ALSPT stock was assumed to be a single biological unit matching AL's management unit (Mississippi-AL border to AL-Florida border); therefore, a single-area model was used.

LIFE HISTORY

The sex-specific LWRs were fixed throughout the assessment period. Growth was modelled using sex-specific VBGFs. The CAAL data were used to assist in the internal estimation of VBGF parameters. During model building, an attempt was made to estimate both sex-specific k and L_{∞} (L_{Amax} in SS3). However, the estimation of k led to failed convergence and model instability (e.g., parameters estimated at bounds). Thus, only the sex-specific L_{Amax} parameters were internally estimated. The mean length of the first reference age (L_{Amin}) was fixed and informed by the developed VBGFs. Two additional parameters are used by the model to capture variability in size-at-age, the CVs at minimum and maximum age modelled (L_{Amin} and L_{Amax} , respectively). Both CVs were fixed at 0.1.

M was assumed to be constant over time and was initially parameterized as a single parameter (option 0 in SS3). To capture a decrease in M with age, explorations considered reparameterizing to a Lorenzen function (option 2 in SS3), age-range Lorenzen (option 6 in SS3), and age-specific (option 3 in SS3) using fixed values; however, all three options led to the model not converging and parameter estimations at bounds. Thus, M was kept as a single parameter.

RECRUITMENT DYNAMICS

A Beverton-Holt stock-recruit relationship was used to parameterize the relationship between spawning output and recruitment of age-0 individuals. The function provides the arithmetic mean of stock-recruit levels and has three parameters: the steepness (h), virgin recruitment estimated in log-space ($\ln R_0$), and the recruitment variability (σ_R , the standard deviation of the log recruitment). σ_R was fixed at 0.3 while h and $\ln R_0$ were both internally estimated. However, the attempt at estimating h led to its estimation at bounds ($h=1$). Thus, h was fixed to the value used in the previous assessment (0.87). Recruitment deviations were estimated for the entirety of the assessment period as a deviation vector with full bias adjustment.

FLEET STRUCTURE AND SURVEY

Five fleets were included in the model: a commercial fleet (Commercial), three recreational fleets to capture changes in selectivity as a result of management changes (Recreational 1981-1999, Recreational 2000-2019, Recreational 2020-2023), and one survey fleet (GNS). These all had accompanying length compositions, except the commercial fleet. The three fleets with the most recent years (Recreational 2000-2019, Recreational 2020-2023, and GNS) also had accompanying CAAL data.

SELECTIVITY

All fleets used length-based selectivity, and patterns were assumed to be constant over time. The recreational fleets were parameterized using logistic functions, while the commercial and survey fleets used dome-shaped (double normal) functions. These were internally estimated, except for the commercial fleet, which lacked biological compositions. Like the previous assessment, the commercial fleet's selectivity function was fixed to have a broad selectivity (while dome-shaped) since management measures were lacking during its practice.

LANDINGS, DISCARDS, AND BIOLOGICAL COMPOSITIONS

Landings were composed of pooled harvest and dead discards, and these were assumed to be "true" observations by having standard errors = 0.01. The Dirichlet Multinomial is a scalar of input sample size for biological compositions, and it is the most applied weighting approach used in SS3 models in the southeastern U.S. (SEDAR 2022,

2025). This was the first weighting approach considered; however, it led to model instability (parameters estimated at bounds and with high gradients). Thus, the Francis approach (Francis 2017), which is a very commonly applied approach for users of SS3, was used instead. The length compositions used 2cm size bins from 5 to 85 cm TL.

MODEL DIAGNOSTICS

Diagnostics were performed following best practices (Carvalho et al. 2021; Kapur et al. 2025). The “ss3diags” (<https://nmfs-ost.github.io/ss3diags/index.html>) and “r4ss” (<https://r4ss.github.io/r4ss/index.html>) packages were used to conduct diagnostics. The following diagnostics were conducted (in the order presented):

1. Model convergence determined by:
 - a) identifying parameter estimations at bounds and/or with gradients with absolute value >0.001 .
 - b) Evaluating the correlation between parameters.
 - c) The final model gradient being relatively small ($<1.00E-04$).
 - d) The Hessian being positive definite, allowing for estimation of parameter variance.
2. Goodness of fit determined by inspections of joint residuals and runs tests on the relative abundance index and length data sources. Root mean squared error (RMSE) was calculated for the joint residuals. The runs tests aid in investigating if any data sources demonstrate any patterns in residuals, which can suggest non-random variation and outliers.
3. Model consistency determined by performing:
 - a) Likelihood profile on $\ln R_0$ and h parameters. $\ln R_0$ was profiled from 6 to 10 at 0.1 increments, while h was profiled from 0.5 to 0.95 in 0.05 increments.
 - b) Jitter analyses applying a 1% and 10% jitter value to starting values and completing 100 model runs for each.
 - c) Retrospective analysis to evaluate the consistency of model estimates by removing the 5 most recent years. Mohn's rho was calculated for all model “peels” to evaluate retrospective patterns.
4. Prediction skill using hindcast cross-validation. Mean absolute scaled error (MASE) was calculated to evaluate forecast bias.

SENSITIVITY RUNS

The following sensitivity runs were conducted:

1. Increasing and decreasing M and h used in the base model by 0.05 (one at a time).
2. Using the average weight of the largest undersized fish (one inch below MSL) corresponding to each management time block for calculating the weight of

dead discards (Table 7). The average weight was derived from the developed length-weight relationship.

3. Dome-shaped selectivity for the most recent recreational time block, to account for discarding fish over the MSL (although there is allowance for one overslot within the bag limit).
4. Reducing the selectivity of the commercial fleet based on anecdotal and expert evidence that the fleet mostly operated using gill nets with 2.5" mesh. The ALSPT length frequency for the GNS small mesh net's 2.5" panel was plotted to inform the parameters.
5. The Marine Recreational Information Program (MRIP) was used to generate a fishery-dependent index for the recreational component of the ALSPT fishery. Data were obtained from the NOAA Fisheries MRIP web portal (<https://www.fisheries.noaa.gov/data-tools/recreational-fisheries-statistics-queries>). This consisted of evaluating multiple proxies of catch divided by the amount of effort. The proxies for catch included 1) MRIP total catch (Type A + B1 + B2), 2) MRIP harvest (Type A + B1), and 3) MRIP observed harvest (Type A). The proxies for effort were the annual number of trips in which ALSPT was the primary or secondary target species (Table 8), and the annual total number of license sales in AL (provided by AMRD staff). The proxies were evaluated by the authors and AMRD staff. Ultimately, it was decided to use total catch and targeted trips as proxies for catch and effort, respectively (Figure 6). This was considered appropriate after verifying that discards (Type B2) had not increased in recent years due to increased harvest restrictions. To develop yearly CVs, the total catch and targeted trips' percent standard error were multiplied and scaled to a mean of 0.3. It is important to note that this sensitivity run is not comparable to the rest in terms of likelihood, as it includes additional indices.

KOBE PLOTS

Kobe plots were developed to track the trajectory of the ALSPT stock biomass and fishing mortality relative to maximum sustainable yield (MSY) and a 30% spawning potential ratio ($SPR_{30\%}$).

COMPARISON TO PREVIOUS ASSESSMENT

Given the ample differences between the modeling approaches, the time between assessments (~10 years), and the management intervention between assessments, a continuity run for the previous assessment was not conducted. Instead, assessment files from the previous assessment were provided by the lead author (Erin C. Bohaboy, NOAA Fisheries), and plots were developed to compare major quantities between assessments.

STOCK ASSESSMENT MODEL RESULTS

ESTIMATED PARAMETERS

The model included 137 parameters, of which 88 were active. No parameters were estimated near bounds or with gradient values >0.001 . A high correlation (>0.7) was only observed between fleet-specific selectivity parameters (e.g., ascending and peak parameters of a selectivity function), which was expected and not concerning.

LANDINGS

Landings begin modestly increasing around the 1980s, followed by sharp increases during the 2000s, and reach their peak ~2010 at >1500 tons (Figure 7). Landings decrease dramatically around 2019 through the end of the time series.

SPAWNING OUTPUT

The relative spawning output initially declines over time, showing a modest decline during the 1950s-1990s, then followed by a dramatic decline from the 1990s to the early 2000s (Figure 8). The relative spawning output falls below the hypothetical management target (0.3) during the early 2000s. This is followed by a sharp increase through 2010, followed by oscillations of the relative spawning output between ~ 0.5 and ~ 1 .

FISHING MORTALITY

F remains under 0.1 until ~ 2000 , followed by a sharp increase in the following years, exceeding 0.5 around 2003 (Figure 9). F is maintained $\sim 0.2-0.3$ for the following ~ 15 years, then it's reduced to ~ 0.1 for the remainder of the time series.

RECRUITMENT

$\ln R_0$ was estimated at 8.48931. Recruitment is stable through ~ 1990 , followed by a decline until the early 2000s (Figure 10). This is followed by a period of relatively high, but variable recruitment for the remainder of the time series. Recruitment deviations demonstrate a strong negative pattern (autocorrelation) during the 1990s through early 2000s, followed by relatively random deviations through the remainder of the time series (Figure 11).

SELECTIVITY

The commercial fleet demonstrates a wide peak with steeper limbs, while the GNS has a much narrower peak with less steep limbs (Figure 12). The length at 50% selection (SL_{50}) for the commercial and GNS are ~ 15 cm (~ 6 "") and 30 cm (~ 12 "") TL, respectively. The SL_{50} for the recreational fleets by time block (oldest to most recent) were ~ 25 (~ 10 ""),

~35 (~14"), and ~35 cm TL. The two most recent recreational time blocks demonstrate similar SL_{50} , but the most recent time block's selectivity peaked at a surprisingly lower length than the previous time block.

MODEL FITS

INDEX

The fit to the GNS was fairly good, demonstrating an increase in the late 2000s, followed by a relatively flat trend (Figure 13). However, the fit does a poor job of capturing several years where the index dramatically increased.

LENGTH COMPOSITIONS

The overall aggregated length composition fits were reasonably good (Figure 14). Some mismatch was observed, especially in the larger sizes of the earliest and most recent recreational fleets. The yearly fits for the earliest recreational time block are somewhat poor, overestimating the mean length during the first half of the time block (Figure 15). The second recreational time block is fitted fairly well, with most years being within confidence intervals and following mean length trends (Figure 16). The most recent time block is the most poorly fitted, with the model overestimating the mean length for most years (Figure 17). The fit to the GNS were generally very good (Figure 18).

AGE COMPOSITIONS

The fits to the yearly mean age from CAAL data were very good for all fleets (Figure 19, Figure 20, Figure 21). The trends in the second recreational time block and GNS are followed very well.

MODEL DIAGNOSTICS

The final gradient and Hessian were 3.36E-05 and 234, respectively. These results, combined with the stable estimation of parameters (e.g., none estimated at bounds nor with absolute gradients >0.001), suggest model convergence. Visual analysis of model fits suggests ample goodness of fit. The joint residual plots indicated a poor fit to the GNS index (RMSE ~58%, Figure 22) and a great fit to the length compositions (RMSE ~8%, Figure 23). There was no evidence ($p \geq 0.05$) to reject the hypothesis of randomly distributed residuals for the GNS (Figure 24). All three length composition data sources evaluated via runs test (the Recreational 2000-2023 fleet was omitted due to the shortness of the time series) showed evidence to reject the hypothesis of randomly distributed residuals (Figure 25). Data points beyond the 3-sigma limit were observed during 1981, 2000, and 2003.

Likelihood profiles of $\ln R_0$ and h revealed that global solutions for these parameters were ~ 8.49 and 0.85 , respectively. The base model estimated $\ln R_0 \sim 8.49$ and h was fixed at 0.87 , which were both within 3 likelihood units of the global solutions. For the $\ln R_0$ profile, recruitment and the length and age compositions appear to be the most influential data sources (Figure 26), while in the h profile, it appears to be recruitment and length compositions (Figure 27). These results support model consistency.

The jitter analyses revealed no runs with a likelihood lower than the base model's (1649). For the 1% jitters, 30% and 44% of model runs were within one and five likelihood units of the global minima, respectively (Figure 28). For the 10% jitters, 5% and 9% of runs were within one and five likelihood units of the global minima, respectively (Figure 29). These results support that the base model parameter optimization converged to the global solution.

Retrospective analyses revealed considerable retrospective bias for spawning output. Mohn's rho values for spawning output became considerably higher beginning in the -3 years data peel (>0.3), and the spawning output increased with an increase in years removed (Figure 30). Mohn's rho values for fishing mortality remained within the recommended acceptable levels for relatively shorter-lived species (Hurtado-Ferro et al. 2015). Fishing mortality decreased as the years removed increased (Figure 31).

Hindcast cross-validation revealed the GNS index demonstrated superior prediction skill (MASE <1 , Figure 32). All tested length composition data sources (Recreational 1981-1999 was omitted since it does not cover recent years) did not show superior predictive skill (MASE >1 , Figure 33).

SENSITIVITY RUNS

Most of the sensitivities fell within confidence intervals of the base model's spawning output and F (Figure 34 and Figure 35). The most notable disagreements with the base model were observed in the sensitivity runs that included a fishery-dependent index and that converted the selectivity of the most recent recreational time block (2020-2023) from logistic to dome-shaped. The inclusion of the fishery-dependent index reduced the scale of the spawning output and increased F , while the change in recreational selectivity did the opposite (relative to the base model).

KOBE PLOTS

The MSY Kobe plot revealed two years when the stock was overfished (2003 and 2004, Figure 36). The SPR_{30%} Kobe plot revealed that the stock was experiencing overfishing for one year (2001), followed by being overfished and experiencing overfishing during two years (2002 and 2003), and being overfished during two years (2004 and 2005, Figure 37). The SPR at MSY was calculated as 23%; thus, it is not surprising that the stock

demonstrates better condition when using MSY-based reference points (e.g., the $SPR_{30\%}$ reference points are conservative relative to MSY).

COMPARISON TO PREVIOUS ASSESSMENT

The base model estimates for SPR and F were plotted with those from the previous assessment (Figure 38 and Figure 39). While the models have different start years, the patterns for overlapping "data-rich" years (1981- 2016) show very similar trends for both quantities. The most notable differences are in terms of ratio. The base model predicts higher SPR throughout overlapping years. While a similar trend can be observed for F , where the base model predicts lower values, some years share very similar values, and the base model predicts relatively higher values in some years. Stark differences can be observed starting ~2000, where the base model estimates improving stock condition (e.g., higher SPR and lower F), while the previous model estimates deteriorating stock condition through its terminal year (2016).

DISCUSSION AND RESEARCH RECOMMENDATIONS

A significant number of new or improved procedures and methodologies were included in this assessment. These include the internal estimation of life history parameters, using multiple longevity-based estimators to inform M , the use of CAAL, the index standardization procedure, and implementing a weighting approach for the biological compositions. Additionally, a full suite of tools was used to diagnose the model and account for uncertainty and assumptions. Despite that, limitations were also present. The most notable being the use of a single parameter M and using the Francis approach to weight biological compositions, despite alternative approaches being strongly recommended across the study region (e.g., Lorenzen function and Dirichlet-Multinomial weighting). Attempts were made to use these, but they resulted in model instability. Nevertheless, we strongly believe the developed model can provide management advice on the ALSPT resource.

There is a need for transparency and detailed documentation of the decision-making in stock assessment model building. In this assessment, documented best practices were followed as much as possible. However, many of these led to model instability and the use of alternative approaches. While the estimation of some of these is data-dependent (e.g., internal estimation of life history parameters), some configurations may be more dependent on when in the model-building process they are implemented (e.g., M parameterization and weighting approach). Therefore, we recommend increased transparency and documentation of stock assessment model building to increase comparability across assessments and the efficiency of analysts.

The ALSPT resource has evidently undergone drastic changes in population size across the last ~30 years. Landings began to drastically increase around the 2000s, which corresponds to the highest F_s and lowest relative spawning output estimated by the model. While landings continued to increase in the 2010s, the model estimated relatively moderate F_s and the spawning output rebuilding from that depleted period in the 2000s. Recruitment is likely very responsible for the differences in stock condition during these two decades. Recruitment during the early 2000s was among the lowest values in the time series, followed by the strongest recruitment in the 2010s, which was apparently able to support the highest landings in the time series.

Sustained F_s in the late 2010s reduced relative spawning output considerably. This was a major finding of the previous assessment, which led to the most recent management intervention in 2019. While the base model estimated depletion during this period, it was not as drastic as the previous assessment estimated (Figure 38). Yet, the base model captures a significant reduction in landings and improved stock condition since this management intervention. While the differences in scale between the models may be due to the many changes in model configuration (e.g., changes in M), the base model corroborates the stock status results from the previous assessment and the subsequent

management intervention. The base model suggests that the ALSPT resource is in the best condition it has been in decades and that AMRD's recent management intervention was a successful one. This is supported by anecdotal reports from local fishing guides and stakeholders (S. P. Powers, J. Mareska, and D. Kiene, pers. comm.).

The drastic reduction in landings during the terminal years presents a challenge to assess the scale and status of the ALSPT resource moving forward. To address this, several fishery-dependent data sets were considered for inclusion in the model as an index. The one that seemed most appropriate for inclusion (total catch per targeted trips) led to model instability (e.g., parameters estimated at bounds and poor results in jitter analysis). Given the present nature of the fishery, with reduced landings and discards (Figure 40), a fishery-dependent index may prove beneficial moving forward to track stock trends.

A fixed discard mortality rate was used in the base model. A sensitivity run was conducted to address this weight assumption and resulted in negligible changes. A lot of consideration must be given to the estimation of discard mortality rates as these may be influenced by spatiotemporal variables as well as fishery demographics (e.g., angler experience level). A catch-and-release mortality study in Texas suggests that short-term post-release mortality of SPT was low (11%) (Stunz and McKee 2006). However, estimates from a tournament live-release study in AL were relatively high (>30%) (Nelson et al. 2021). While higher post-release mortality may be expected from a weigh-in tournament (e.g., higher handling time), these disparities in post-release mortality highlight the careful attention needed when calculating discard mortality, especially in a stock assessment application.

Spatiotemporal changes in life history parameters, such as M and h , should be considered in future assessments. The estimation of these requires thoughtful consideration, as they greatly affect stock productivity and resilience to fishing pressure. A tag-return study from the U.S. South Atlantic reported a higher annual M value than the one used in the region's most recent stock assessment (Ellis et al. 2018). Further, this study demonstrated elevated M during the winter season (e.g., thermal stress). The ongoing AL tag-return study (<https://www.southalabama.edu/colleges/artsandsci/marinesciences/tag-alabama.html>) will be greatly beneficial for exploring the fine-scale temporal changes in M of the ALSPT resource. We recommend the consideration of state-space models (e.g., Woods Hole Assessment Model) to explore time-varying parameters in future ALSPT assessments.

A clear 2:1 female skew in the sex ratio was observed in the biological samples used to inform the assessment (Table 2 and Table 3). This was documented to a stronger degree in Tampa Bay, Florida, with females outnumbering males 8:1 at harvestable sizes (Carroll and Lowerre-Barbieri 2019). The authors hypothesize that this is due to females attaining

larger length-at-age (as observed in this assessment), as well as males displaying lower somatic growth due to reproductive behaviors and higher natural mortality due to increased predation risk (Carroll and Lowerre-Barbieri 2019). While this hypothesis can explain the observed skew in sex ratio, the oldest fish included in this assessment were males (Figure 1). This observation leads to the question of whether the population is simultaneously female-skewed while males are more cryptic to the fishery. Anecdotal reports indicate that large SPT can be observed in the AL nearshore reefs (D. Kiene, pers. comm.). As such, we recommend the use of lethal and non-lethal tools (e.g., otolith microchemistry and acoustic tags) to further understand the population dynamics and sex-specific movement ecology of SPT.

Residual patterns (autocorrelation) were very evident in the recruitment deviation time series. These patterns suggest that some of the recruitment dynamics may be driven by some external processes that the model does not explicitly account for. Other states have highlighted how environmental variables can drive the recruitment success of SPT. Among these are freshwater discharge, temperature, salinity, and the presence and abundance of structured and vegetated habitats (Flaherty-Walia et al. 2015; Whaley et al. 2016, 2023; Nehemiah et al. 2022; Eckert et al. 2025). Investigations into environment-recruitment relationships of ALSPT, with the goal of further understanding recruitment dynamics and explicitly accounting for these within a stock assessment framework, are ongoing (Coffill-Rivera et al., in prep).

Recently, there has been an increase in regional outreach and stakeholder awareness of practicing catch-and-release, especially for larger fish (<https://releaseover20.org/>). Theoretically, this should lower F while maintaining high spawning biomass. However, increased participation in the recreational sector may be counteracting this, as there may be more effort and harvest bottlenecking the recruitment of fish into >20" (50.8 cm) TL size classes. Increasing effort and changing fisher behaviors are mechanisms to consider when evaluating stock assessment results.

The results from this assessment highlight the exemplary efforts AMRD has taken to conserve and manage its fishery resources. The 2019 management intervention also included changes to the harvest of Southern Flounder *Paralichthys lethostigma* in AL, which was experiencing high exploitation rates and low spawning biomass (Powers et al. 2018). The changes included reducing bag limits, increasing the MSL, and implementing a harvest moratorium during the spawning season (ADCNR 2019b). A recent assessment of the resource suggests that the spawning biomass is on track to rebuild while experiencing sustainable levels of exploitation since the management intervention (D. Kiene et al., in prep). Regarding SPT, the stock condition in AL seems to be among the best across the Gulf states. The recent Florida SPT assessment indicates the Gulf stock is in remarkable condition (Addis et al. 2025) (Addis et al. 2025). The most recent assessment in Louisiana strongly suggests their SPT resource has been severely

overfished and has been experiencing overfishing for over a decade (West et al. 2021). The most recent assessment in Mississippi suggests their SPT resource is experiencing increasing F and decreasing biomass (Leaf and Hendon 2016). It is important to note that states use different reference points to assess their fishery resources. Given the absence of reference points in AL (at least for SPT), we recommend their adoption as a future step to manage fishery resources consistently without “moving the goalpost”.

This assessment assumed the AL management jurisdiction matched the biological unit of the ALSPT resource. Given the reproductive behaviors of SPT and the waterbodies shared between states (e.g., Perdido Bay being shared by AL and Florida), it is very likely that this assumption is not true. The recent SPT assessment in Florida converted its Gulf stock from multiple units into one based on genetic work, suggesting no hard genetic breaks along the state coast (Addis et al. 2025). It is very likely that the actual SPT biological units in the Gulf are shared between states, especially between AL, Florida, and Mississippi. As such, there should be strong consideration for collaborative management, as management decisions in one jurisdiction could strongly affect stock condition in another.

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DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

Assessment files and supplementary figures and tables are openly available in the following GitHub repository (<https://github.com/manuelcofill/AL-Spotted-SeatROUT-stock-assessment>). Questions regarding the assessment can be directed at the lead author via email (manuelcofill@gmail.com).

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TABLES

Table 1: Summarized management history of the Alabama stock of Spotted Seatrout *Cynoscion nebulosus*.

Year	Description
1978	Recreational minimum size limit (MSL) of 12" (30.5 cm) total length (TL) and daily bag limit of 50 fish per person (pp)
1985	Designation of game fish status and permanent closure of commercial fishery
1986	Recreational MSL increased to 14" (35.6 cm) TL, daily bag limit of 10 fish pp, and undersized allowance
2000	Removal of undersized allowance from previous action
2019	Implementation of recreational slot limit of 15-22" (38.1-55.9 cm) TL and daily bag limit of 6 fish pp with one overslot allowance

Table 2: Sex-specific von Bertalanffy growth model parameters for the Alabama stock of Spotted Seatrout *Cynoscion nebulosus* using data collected during 2000-2023.

	L_{∞} (cm TL)	k	t_0	n
Female	71.7	0.24	-0.67	4922
Male	59.5	0.23	-0.86	2470

Table 3: Sex-specific length-weight relationship parameters for the Alabama stock of Spotted Seatrout *Cynoscion nebulosus* using data collected during 2000-2024.

	a	B	R^2	n
Female	1.09×10^{-5}	2.97	0.96	5621
Male	1.15×10^{-5}	2.95	0.96	2612

Table 4: Options used to query recreational catch of the Alabama stock of Spotted Seatrout *Cynoscion nebulosus*.

Parameter	Option
From	1981
To	2023
Summarize by	Annual
Fishing year	Calendar year
Geographical area	Alabama
Species	Spotted Seatrout
Type of fishing	All modes combined
Fishing area	All areas combined
Type of catch	Harvest (Type A + B1)

Table 5: Options used to query commercial catch of the Alabama stock of Spotted Seatrout *Cynoscion nebulosus*.

Parameter	Option
Data set	Commercial
Year	1950-2022
Region type	State
State landed	Alabama
Species	Seatrout, spotted
Report format	Totals by year

Table 6: Options used to query recreational length compositions of the Alabama stock of Spotted Seatrout *Cynoscion nebulosus*.

From	1981
To	2023
Summarize	By year
Fishing year	Calendar
Geographical area	Alabama
Species	Spotted Seatrout
Type of fishing	All modes combined
Fishing area	All areas combined
Information	Straight fork length (centimeters)
Size of length bin	2

Table 7: Lengths and weights used for the sensitivity run that used the weight of the largest undersized fish as the weight of dead discards by management time block.

Rec period	MSL – 1”	Total length (cm)	Weight (kg)
1981-1999	11	28	0.25
2000-2019	13	33	0.5
2020-2023	14	35	0.5

Table 8: Options used to query the number of trips in which of the Alabama stock of Spotted Seatrout *Cynoscion nebulosus* was the primary or secondary target species.

From	1981
To	2023
Summarize	By year
Fishing year	Calendar
Geographical area	Alabama
Species	Spotted Seatrout
Type of fishing	All modes combined
Fishing area	All areas combined
Species option	Primary target, secondary target
Information	Directed angler trips

FIGURES

Figure 1: Sex-specific growth models for the Alabama stock of Spotted Seatrout *Cynoscion nebulosus* using data collected during 2000-2023.

Figure 2: Sex-specific length-weight relationship of the Alabama stock of Spotted Seatrout *Cynoscion nebulosus* using data collected during 2000-2024.

Figure 3: Density distributions of longevity-based natural mortality estimators for the Alabama stock of Spotted Seatrout *Cynoscion nebulosus*.

Figure 4: Alabama Marine Resources Division's Gill Net Survey stations (small mesh only) during 2001-2023 that were included in the Spotted Seatrout *Cynoscion nebulosus* relative abundance index development. Red symbols denote stations with no Spotted Seatrout catch, while green points denote stations with Spotted Seatrout catch and point size reflecting abundance.

Figure 5: Standardized catch of Spotted Seatrout *Cynoscion nebulosus* from the Alabama Marine Resources Division's Gill Net Survey (small mesh only) during 2001 - 2023. Purple points and line denote the mean predictions while keeping retained covariates at mean values, and purple ribbon denotes the 95% confidence intervals. Note these values are back-transformed from the 4th root transformation of the response variable standardized using a generalized additive model framework with a negative binomial error type. Teal points and line denote the nominal values.

Figure 6: Total catch (number of individuals) per number of targeted trips (primary or secondary target) of the Alabama stock of Spotted Seatrout *Cynoscion nebulosus*.

Figure 7: Stacked fleet-specific landings of the Alabama stock of Spotted Seatrout *Cynoscion nebulosus*. Note that landings include dead discards.

Figure 8: Relative spawning output of the Alabama stock of Spotted Seatrout *Cynoscion nebulosus* with ~95% asymptotic intervals.

Figure 9: Fishing mortality rates with 95% intervals of the Alabama stock of Spotted Seatrout *Cynoscion nebulosus*.

Figure 10: Recruitment with ~95% asymptotic intervals of the Alabama stock of Spotted Seatrout *Cynoscion nebulosus*.

Figure 11: Recruitment deviations with 95% intervals of the Alabama stock of Spotted Seatrout *Cynoscion nebulosus*.

Figure 12: Fleet-specific length-based selectivity of the Alabama stock of Spotted Seatrout *Cynoscion nebulosus*.

Figure 13: Fit to Alabama Marine Resources Division's Gill Net Survey. Lines indicate 95% uncertainty interval around index values based on the model assumption of lognormal error.

Figure 14: Fits to fleet-specific aggregated length compositions.

Figure 15: Fit to the yearly mean length of the earliest recreational time block with 95% confidence intervals based on current sample sizes.

Figure 16: Fit to the yearly mean length of the middle recreational time block with 95% confidence intervals based on current sample sizes.

Figure 17: Fit to the yearly mean length of the most recent recreational time block with 95% confidence intervals based on current sample sizes.

Figure 18: Fit to the yearly mean length of the Alabama Marine Resources Division's Gill Net Survey with 95% confidence intervals based on current sample sizes.

Figure 19: Fit to the yearly mean age from conditional data (aggregated across length bins) of the middle recreational time block with 95% confidence intervals based on current sample sizes.

Figure 20: Fit to the yearly mean age from conditional data (aggregated across length bins) of the most recent recreational time block with 95% confidence intervals based on current sample sizes.

Figure 21: Fit to the yearly mean age from conditional data (aggregated across length bins) of the Alabama Marine Resources Division's Gill Net Survey with 95% confidence intervals based on current sample sizes.

Figure 22: Joint residual plot for the index fit. Vertical lines with points denote the residuals, and the solid black line represents the loess smoother. The root mean squared error (RMSE) is provided within the plot.

Figure 23: Joint residual plot for the mean length fit. Vertical lines with points denote the residuals color-coded by fleet, and the solid black line represents the loess smoother. The root mean squared error (RMSE) is provided within the plot.

Figure 24: Runs test for the index fit. The green shading indicates no evidence ($p \geq 0.05$) to reject the hypothesis of a randomly distributed time series of residuals. The shaded area spans three residual standard deviations to either side of zero.

Figure 25: Runs test for the mean length fits. The red shading indicates evidence ($p < 0.05$) to reject the hypothesis of a randomly distributed time series of residuals. The shaded area spans three residual standard deviations to either side of zero. The red points outside of the shading violate the 'three-sigma limit' for that time series.

Figure 26: Likelihood profile of the natural log of the unfished recruitment parameter of the Beverton-Holt stock-recruit relationship of the Alabama stock of Spotted Seatrout *Cynoscion nebulosus*. Lines represent changes in the negative log likelihood and are color-coded by fleet. Panels demonstrate changes in the negative log likelihood by data type.

Figure 27: Likelihood profile of the steepness parameter of the Beverton-Holt stock-recruit relationship of the Alabama stock of Spotted Seatrout *Cynoscion nebulosus*. Lines represent changes in the negative log likelihood and are color-coded by fleet. Panels demonstrate changes in the negative log likelihood by data type.

Figure 28: Results from the jitter analysis, randomly changing starting parameter values by 1% for 100 model runs. No runs revealed a negative log likelihood lower than the base model.

Figure 29: Results from the jitter analysis, randomly changing starting parameter values by 10% for 100 model runs. No runs revealed a negative log likelihood lower than the base model.

Figure 30: Results from the five-year retrospective analysis for spawning output of the Alabama stock of Spotted Seatrout *Cynoscion nebulosus*. The shaded area represents the base model's 95% confidence intervals. Data peels are color-coded, and their Mohn's rho values are provided.

Figure 31: Results from the five-year retrospective analysis for fishing mortality of the Alabama stock of Spotted Seatrout *Cynoscion nebulosus*. The shaded area represents the base model's 95% confidence intervals. Data peels are color-coded, and their Mohn's rho values are provided.

Figure 32: Hindcast cross-validation (HCxval) results of the index fit. The observations are denoted by the large points connected by the dotted line. The fits are denoted by the solid lines. One-year-ahead forecast values are denoted by smaller terminal points. HCxval was performed using one reference model (Ref) and five hindcast model runs (solid lines) relative to the expected index. The observations used for cross-validation are highlighted as color-coded solid circles with associated 95 % confidence intervals (light-gray shading). The model reference year refers to the endpoints of each one-year-ahead forecast and the corresponding observation (e.g., year of peel + 1). The mean absolute scaled error (MASE) is provided.

Figure 33: Hindcast cross-validation (HCxval) results of the mean length fits. The observations are denoted by the large points connected by the dotted line. The fits are denoted by the solid lines. One-year-ahead forecast values are denoted by smaller terminal points. HCxval was performed using one reference model (Ref) and five hindcast model runs (solid lines) relative to the expected index. The observations used for cross-validation are highlighted as color-coded solid circles with associated 95 % confidence intervals (light-gray shading). The model reference year refers to the endpoints of each one-year-ahead forecast and the corresponding observation (e.g., year of peel + 1). The mean absolute scaled error (MASE) is provided.

Figure 34: Spawning output estimates from the sensitivity analysis.

Figure 35: Fishing mortality estimates from the sensitivity analysis.

Figure 36: Kobe plot illustrating the trajectory of the Alabama stock of Spotted Seatrout *Cynoscion nebulosus* relative to reference points based on maximum sustainable yield. The blue and purple dots denote the model start and terminal years, respectively.

Figure 37: Kobe plot illustrating the trajectory of the Alabama stock of Spotted Seatrout *Cynoscion nebulosus* relative to reference points based on a 30% spawning potential ratio. The blue and purple dots denote the model start and terminal years, respectively.

Figure 38: Comparison of spawning potential ratio (SPR) estimates between the base model and the previous assessment.

Figure 39: Comparison of fishing mortality (F) estimates between the base model and the previous assessment.

Figure 40: Discards (number of individuals) of the Alabama stock of Spotted Seatrout *Cynoscion nebulosus*.